

Performance of time-to-event methods in delayed treatment effect scenarios - A simulation plan

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This document describes the ADEMP structure as introduced by Morris et al. (2019) for the examination of type I error and power of methods to analyse time-to-event data.

1 Notation

Let $(t_1, d_1, x_1), \dots, (t_n, d_n, x_n)$ denote the observations of n patients, where t_j denotes the observed event or censoring time, d_j denotes the event indicator and x_j indicates whether the patient belongs to the control or experimental group. The following processes describe if and how many patients (per group g) are at risk at time t .

$$\bar{Y}_g(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n 1(t_i \geq t, x_i = g), \quad \bar{Y}(t) = \bar{Y}_0(t) + \bar{Y}_1(t)$$

Furthermore, the processes

$$\bar{N}_g(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n 1(t_i \leq t, d_i = 1, x_i = g), \quad \bar{N}(t) = \bar{N}_0(t) + \bar{N}_1(t)$$

denote if and how many failures (per group g) occur up to and including time t . The number of failures in group g at a given time t is denoted with $\Delta \bar{N}_g(t) = \bar{N}_g(t) - \bar{N}_g(t-)$. The total number in both groups will again be denoted without index.

Furthermore, $\hat{S}_g(t)$ denotes the Kaplan-Meier estimator in group g , whereas $\hat{S}(t)$ denotes the Kaplan-Meier estimator in the pooled sample. Lastly the Nelson-Aalen estimator of the cumulative hazard is denoted with $\hat{\Lambda}_{NA}(t)$

2 Assessment of Power

In the following the ADEMP structure of the power assessment is described in detail.

Aim

To assess the power of the different methods in settings with a delayed treatment effect more thoroughly and investigate how the duration of the delay impacts the rejection probability of the method.

Data-generating mechanism

For the data-generating mechanism the following parameters were chosen:

- As can be seen in clinical trials in the field of immuno-oncology the study duration and accrual is quite heterogeneous. For example in the CHECKMATE 078 patients were enrolled for 12 months (December 2015 to November 2016) and the database was locked on October 27, 2017, so that the total duration of the study was 23 months and hence the proportion of accrual on the study duration was approx. 50%. In contrast the CHECKMATE 067 enrolled patients for 9 months (July 3, 2013 to March 31, 2014) but had a total study duration of 58 months (database lock on May 10, 2018) giving proportion of approx. 16% if the accrual on the total study duration. To take this into account the study duration was taken to be

$$\tau = 6, 12, 24, 48, 60$$

- Uniform accrual over the interval $[0, a]$, where a is expressed as fraction of the total study duration τ , i.e. $a = 0.2\tau, 0.4\tau$.
- The delayed treatment effect occurs with a delay of $t_2^* = 0, 0.1\tau, 0.2\tau, 0.3\tau, 0.4\tau$.
- The hazard ratio θ of the full treatment effect varies $\theta = 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8$

- The hazards $h_C(t)$ and $h_T(t)$ of the control and treatment arm, respectively, can be expressed in terms of a general lag model, i.e.

$$h_T(t) = [1 - l(t) + \theta l(t)]h_C(t),$$

with a monotone non-decreasing lag function $0 \leq l(t) \leq 1$. The lag function is taken to represent the following 3 delay patterns:

- Threshold lag with a change point t^* : $l(t) = I(t \geq t^*)$,
- Linear lag with change point t^* : $l(t) = \frac{t}{t^*}I(t < t^*) + I(t \geq t^*)$ or
- Generalized linear lag with change points t_1^*, t_2^* : $l(t) = \frac{t-t_1^*}{t_2^*-t_1^*}I(t_1^* \leq t < t_2^*) + I(t \geq t_2^*)$.

It can be easily seen that the linear lag and the threshold lag are contained in the generalized linear lag pattern by choosing $t_1^* = 0$ or $t_1^* = t_2^*$, respectively. The change point t_1^* will be chosen as proportion of the lag t_2^* , meaning

$$t_1^* = 0.3t_2^*, 0.7t_2^*, t_2^*.$$

- The distribution of survival times in the control group is chosen to be Weibull distributed $\text{Wei}(\lambda_C, k_C)$ with shape parameter k_C reflecting the following types of hazards:
 - decreasing hazard: $k_C = 0.5$
 - constant hazard (exponential): $k_C = 1$
 - (linearly) increasing hazard: $k_C = 2$

scale parameter λ_C chosen in dependence on the aspired median survival times. Since the observed median survival times in the control arms of the above mentioned CHECK-MATE trials ranges from 2.3 to 4.2 months in PFS and from 5.1 to 19.9 months in OS, we considered median survival times of

$$\text{med}_C = 5, 15, 20$$

and calculated the scale parameter as $\lambda_C = \frac{(\ln(2))^{1/k_C}}{\text{med}_C}$.

To calculate the total number of scenarios one has to keep in mind that if $t_2^* = 0$, i.e. no delay is assumed, there will also no changepoint present based on the model under consideration. Thus the total number of simulated scenarios described above will be $5 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 + 5 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 = 4680$.

Starting with exponentially distributed survival times in the control group ($k_C = 1$), a fixed medium study duration of $\tau = 24$ and a hazard ratio of $\theta = 0.5$ the number of scenarios is reduced to 78.

Next these results will be contrasted to scenarios with the same study duration, but the lowest hazard ratio of $\theta = 0.8$. For now it is assumed that only administrative censoring is present in the data.

To set a benchmark for the analysis three different strategies for sample size calculation were pursued and the necessary number of observations n_{obs} needed to achieve a power of 80% was calculated assuming proportional hazards and an hazard ratio of:

- the full effect θ , reflecting that at the time of planning the trial there was no evidence for treatment delay.
- the naive average effect $\frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \frac{h_T(t)}{h_C(t)} dt$
- the average effect $\frac{1}{\tau} \int_0^\tau \frac{h_T(t)}{h_C(t)} S_p(t) dt$ based on the pooled survival function in both arms, i.e. $S_p(t) = \frac{1}{2}(S_T(t) + S_C(t))$

This was done using the `rpact` package based on the sample size calculation method by Schoenfeld (Wassmer and Pahlke, 2023).

Full effect

Using the full effect reduces the number of scenarios for which the sample size needs to be calculated to 6 since n_{obs} only depends on the median survival in the control arm and the accrual time.

Table 1: *Sample size for the scenario without lag and HR of 0.5 to achieve power of 80%*

Accrual proportion	Median survival in control arm	Number of observations
0.2	5	76
0.4	5	80
0.2	15	128
0.4	15	140
0.2	20	156
0.4	20	172

Naive average hazard ratio

The naive average hazard ratio is obtained by integrating the assumed general linear lag model function, which yields the following n_{obs} .

Table 2: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 5$ planned on the naive average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Naive Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	76
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	80
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.2	92
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.4	96
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.2	96
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.4	100
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.2	102
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.4	106
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.2	110
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.4	114
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.2	124
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.4	128
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.2	136
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.4	142
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.2	134
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.4	138
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.2	162
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.4	168
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.2	188
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.4	196
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.2	164
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.4	170
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.2	216
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.4	224
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.2	272
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.4	280

Table 3: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 15$ planned on the naive average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Naive Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	128
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	140
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.2	152
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.4	166
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.2	162
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.4	174
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.2	168
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.4	182
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.2	182
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.4	198
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.2	204
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.4	222
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.2	224
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.4	242
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.2	220
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.4	240
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.2	264
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.4	288
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.2	306
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.4	332
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.2	270
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.4	292
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.2	352
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.4	380
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.2	436
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.4	474

Table 4: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 20$ planned on the naive average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Naive Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	156
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	172
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.2	186
0.1	0.3	0.53	0.4	204
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.2	196
0.1	0.7	0.54	0.4	214
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.2	204
0.1	1.0	0.55	0.4	224
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.2	222
0.2	0.3	0.56	0.4	244
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.2	250
0.2	0.7	0.58	0.4	272
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.2	272
0.2	1.0	0.60	0.4	298
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.2	268
0.3	0.3	0.60	0.4	294
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.2	322
0.3	0.7	0.63	0.4	352
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.2	372
0.3	1.0	0.65	0.4	406
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.2	328
0.4	0.3	0.63	0.4	358
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.2	426
0.4	0.7	0.67	0.4	466
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.2	530
0.4	1.0	0.70	0.4	578

Average hazard ratio

The average hazard ratio based on the pooled survival function gives the following sample sizes n_{obs} .

Table 5: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 5$ planned on the average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	78
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	80
0.1	0.3	0.60	0.2	142
0.1	0.3	0.60	0.4	148
0.1	0.7	0.63	0.2	176
0.1	0.7	0.63	0.4	182
0.1	1.0	0.66	0.2	204
0.1	1.0	0.66	0.4	210
0.2	0.3	0.68	0.2	248
0.2	0.3	0.68	0.4	256
0.2	0.7	0.73	0.2	370
0.2	0.7	0.73	0.4	384
0.2	1.0	0.77	0.2	494
0.2	1.0	0.77	0.4	510
0.3	0.3	0.75	0.2	418
0.3	0.3	0.75	0.4	432
0.3	0.7	0.81	0.2	762
0.3	0.7	0.81	0.4	784
0.3	1.0	0.84	0.2	1166
0.3	1.0	0.84	0.4	1198
0.4	0.3	0.80	0.2	688
0.4	0.3	0.80	0.4	710
0.4	0.7	0.86	0.2	1540
0.4	0.7	0.86	0.4	1584
0.4	1.0	0.89	0.2	2736
0.4	1.0	0.89	0.4	2808

Table 6: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 15$ planned on the average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	130
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	142
0.1	0.3	0.56	0.2	180
0.1	0.3	0.56	0.4	196
0.1	0.7	0.58	0.2	202
0.1	0.7	0.58	0.4	220
0.1	1.0	0.59	0.2	220
0.1	1.0	0.59	0.4	238
0.2	0.3	0.61	0.2	246
0.2	0.3	0.61	0.4	266
0.2	0.7	0.65	0.2	310
0.2	0.7	0.65	0.4	336
0.2	1.0	0.67	0.2	368
0.2	1.0	0.67	0.4	396
0.3	0.3	0.66	0.2	338
0.3	0.3	0.66	0.4	364
0.3	0.7	0.71	0.2	476
0.3	0.7	0.71	0.4	512
0.3	1.0	0.74	0.2	618
0.3	1.0	0.74	0.4	662
0.4	0.3	0.70	0.2	460
0.4	0.3	0.70	0.4	496
0.4	0.7	0.76	0.2	738
0.4	0.7	0.76	0.4	790
0.4	1.0	0.80	0.2	1056
0.4	1.0	0.80	0.4	1130

Table 7: *Sample size for the scenario with $\text{med}_C = 20$ planned on the average HR to achieve power of 80%*

t_2^*	t_1^*	Average HR	Accrual proportion	Number of observations
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.2	158
0.0	0.0	0.50	0.4	174
0.1	0.3	0.55	0.2	214
0.1	0.3	0.55	0.4	232
0.1	0.7	0.57	0.2	236
0.1	0.7	0.57	0.4	256
0.1	1.0	0.59	0.2	254
0.1	1.0	0.59	0.4	278
0.2	0.3	0.60	0.2	284
0.2	0.3	0.60	0.4	310
0.2	0.7	0.64	0.2	352
0.2	0.7	0.64	0.4	382
0.2	1.0	0.66	0.2	408
0.2	1.0	0.66	0.4	444
0.3	0.3	0.65	0.2	380
0.3	0.3	0.65	0.4	412
0.3	0.7	0.69	0.2	522
0.3	0.7	0.69	0.4	564
0.3	1.0	0.72	0.2	662
0.3	1.0	0.72	0.4	716
0.4	0.3	0.69	0.2	504
0.4	0.3	0.69	0.4	546
0.4	0.7	0.74	0.2	782
0.4	0.7	0.74	0.4	844
0.4	1.0	0.78	0.2	1094
0.4	1.0	0.78	0.4	1180

Estimand and Methods

This simulation study is designed to assess the power of the following methods to compare two groups:

- **Weighted Log-rank tests:**

1. **Fleming-Harrington ($G(\rho, \gamma)$):**

The Fleming-Harrington family with weights $w(t) = \hat{S}(t-)^{\rho} \cdot (1 - \hat{S}(t-))^{\gamma}$ for

$(\rho, \gamma) = (0, 1), (1, 0), (1, 1), (0, 0.5), (0, 2), (0.5, 0.5), (-1, 0)$ (Fleming and Harrington, 1981). $G(0, 0)$ denotes the standard log-rank test.

2. Modestly weighted logrank test (MWLR):

This test uses the weight $w(t) = \frac{1}{\max(\hat{S}(t), \hat{S}(t^*))}$ (Magirr and Burman, 2019).

3. Threshold lag (Thres) and generalized linear lag (GenLin) test:

The threshold lag test uses weight $w_{t_0}(t) = 1(t \geq t_0)$ (Xu et al., 2017) and the generalized linear lag test uses weights $w_{T_1, T_2}(t) = \frac{t-T_1}{T_2-T_1} \cdot 1(T_1 < t < T_2) + 1(T_2 \leq t)$ (Xu et al., 2018).

4. Gehan-Breslow (GB):

Derived by Gehan (1965) and Breslow (1970) they use weight $w(t) = \bar{Y}(t)$.

5. Tarone-Ware (TW):

Tarone and Ware (1977) uses weight $w(t) = \sqrt{\bar{Y}(t)}$.

6. Peto-Peto (PP) and modified Peto-Peto (mPP):

Peto and Peto (1972) use weights $w(t) = \prod_{i: t_i \leq t} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta N(t_i)}{\bar{Y}(t_i)+1}\right)$ or $w(t) = \prod_{i: t_i \leq t} \left(1 - \frac{\Delta N(t_i)\bar{Y}(t_i)}{(\bar{Y}(t_i)+1)^2}\right)$, respectively.

7. Asymptotic logrank test (asymLR):

Moreau et al. (1992) proposed the weights $w(t) = 1 + \log \left(-\log \left(\prod_{i: t_i \leq t} \frac{\bar{Y}(t_i)}{\bar{Y}(t_i) + \Delta N(t_i)} \right) \right)$

8. Logit and modified Logit (mLogit):

The logit weight function $w(t) = \text{Logit}_{a, \tau}(t) = \frac{\exp(a(t-\tau))}{(1+\exp(a(x-\tau)))}$ and the modified logit weight function $w(t) = \frac{\text{Logit}_{a, \tau}(t) - \text{Logit}_{a, \tau}(t_1)}{\text{Logit}_{a, \tau}(t_2) - \text{Logit}_{a, \tau}(t_1)}$ with scaling parameter a and the parameter τ defined as the middle point of the prespecified transition period (Yu et al., 2021).

9. Maximin efficiency robust test (MERT):

The MERT test uses the weight

$$w_{\tilde{t}_1, \tilde{t}_2}(t) = \left(\frac{\Psi(\tau) - \Psi(t)}{\Psi(\tau) - \Psi(\tilde{t}_1)} \right)^{-1/2} 1(\tilde{t}_1 \leq t \leq \tilde{t}_2) + 2 \left(\frac{\Psi(\tau) - \Psi(\tilde{t}_2)}{\Psi(\tau) - \Psi(\tilde{t}_1)} \right)^{-1/2} 1(t > \tilde{t}_2)$$

where τ is the study duration and $\Psi(t)$ is estimated by

$$\hat{\Psi}(t) = \frac{1}{n} \int_0^t \frac{\bar{Y}_0(u)\bar{Y}_1(u)}{\bar{Y}^2(u)} d\bar{N}(u).$$

• **Combination of weighted log-rank tests**

1. **Max-Combo (MaxCombo):**

The Max-Combo test is defined as $Z_{\max} = \max(|G(0, 0)|, |G(0, 1)|, |G(1, 0)|, |G(1, 1)|)$.

2. **Modified Max-Combo (mMaxCombo):**

Cheng and He (2021) proposed to replace $G(1, 1)$ by a weighted logrank test with weight $w_\theta(t) = 1(\hat{S}(t-) \leq \theta) \frac{\hat{S}(t-) - \theta}{\theta} + 1(\hat{S}(t-) > \theta) \frac{\hat{S}(t-) - \theta}{1 - \theta}$.

3. **Zm3:**

The Zm3 test is defined as $Z_{m_3} = \max(|G(0, 0)|, |G(0, 1)|, |G(1, 0)|)$.

4. **Modified Zm3 (mZm3):**

Royston and Parmar (2020) proposed to replace $G(1, 0)$ by a weighted logrank test with weight $w(t) = \max\left(0.001, \frac{\hat{S}(t-) - \min(\hat{S}(t-))}{1 - \min(\hat{S}(t-))}\right)$.

5. **Versatile tests by Lee (Lee1, Lee2, Lee3):**

Lee (2007) proposed the following versatile combinations:

- Lee1 = $\frac{|G(0,1)+G(1,0)|}{2}$
- Lee2 = $\frac{|G(0,1)|+|G(1,0)|}{2}$
- Lee3 = $\max(|G(0, 1)|, |G(1, 0)|)$

6. **LR+G(1,0):**

The sum $|G(0, 0)| + |G(1, 0)|$ was considered by Yang and Zhao (2007).

7. **max(LR,G(0,1)):**

Callegaro and Spiessens (2017) proposed to use the maximum of logrank and $|G(0, 1)|$.

8. **Projection test:**

Cheng and He (2021) also proposed a projection-type test as

$$(G(0, 0), G(1, 0), W_{w_{0.5}}) \cdot \hat{P}^{-1} \cdot (G(0, 0), G(1, 0), W_{w_{0.5}})^t$$

where \hat{P}^{-1} denotes the Moore-Penrose inverse of the estimated covariance matrix.

9. **Modified Score (mScore):**

Similarly, Bagdonavicius et al. (2004) considered a projection test based on the logrank test and the weighted logrank test with weight $w(t) = \log(1 + \hat{\Lambda}_{NA}(t-))$.

10. **Adaptively weighted logrank test (YP, YP1.LR, YP2.LR):**

Yang and Prentice (2010) used the estimated hazard ratios $\Phi_1(t)$ and $\Phi_2(t)$ based on their semiparametric model as weight.

$$\max(|U_{\Phi_1}|, |U_{\Phi_2}|) \quad (\text{YP})$$

$$\max(|U_{\Phi_1}|, |G(0, 0)|) \quad (\text{YP1.LR})$$

$$\max(|G(0, 0)|, |U_{\Phi_2}|), \quad (\text{YP2.LR})$$

11. **V0:**

As an approximation of the MERT test Ding and Wu (2020) considered the sum of logrank and threshold lag test.

12. **Partially grouped logrank test (ParGroup):**

This is a hybrid between the fixed-time analysis and the usual logrank statistics (Sposto et al., 1997).

13. **Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS LR, KS FH, KS GB, KS Cheng):**

The idea is to take the supremum over all truncation times of the integral for the weighted logrank test. Cheng and He (2021) considered the following weighted logrank tests: standard logrank, Gehan-Breslow, $G(1, 0)$ and the modified weighted logrank test by Cheng.

- **Kaplan-Meier based tests**

1. **Milestone survival (Mile, Mile CLL):**

Comparison of the raw or cloglog transformed survival rates at a fixed timepoint t_0 between both groups (Klein, 2020).

2. **Restricted mean survival time (RMST):**

RMST is defined as $\int_0^\tau (\hat{S}_1(t) - \hat{S}_0(t)) dt$.

3. **Weighted Kaplan-Meier (Weighted KM):**

Pepe and Fleming (1989) introduced a weighted version of the RMST with weight $w(t) = \frac{n\hat{S}_{cens,0}\hat{S}_{cens,1}}{n_0\hat{S}_{cens,1}+n_1\hat{S}_{cens,0}}$ based on the Kaplan-Meier estimator for the censoring times \hat{S}_{cens} in both groups

4. **Adaptively weighted Kaplan-Meier (AWKM1, AWKM2):**

Uno et al. (2015) modified the weight to be $w(t) = \max\left(\frac{\hat{S}_1(t)-\hat{S}_0(t)}{\hat{\sigma}_{\hat{S}_1(t)-\hat{S}_0(t)}}, c\right)$, where c is selected adaptively.

5. **Area between curves (ABC):**

The ABC statistic is very similar to the RMST and defined as $T_n = \sqrt{n} \int_0^\tau |\hat{S}_1(t) - \hat{S}_0(t)| dt$ where τ denotes the largest censoring time (Lin and Xu, 2010) (Liu et al., 2020).

• **Regression model based tests**

The first class of survival regression models are based on modeling the hazard function

$$\lambda(t) = \lambda_0(t) \exp(\beta x).$$

1. **Standard Cox (Cox):**

The standard Cox model as introduced by Cox (1972).

2. **Average hazard ratio (AHR):**

Schemper et al. (2009) proposed to use the inverse probability of censoring weighting, i.e. weight $w(t) = \frac{\hat{S}(t)}{\hat{S}_{cens}(t)}$.

3. **Landmark:**

Consider only events after a prespecified assumed landmark time.

4. **Time-dependent treatment effect (CoxTD):**

Employ a time-varying effect by adding an interaction between x and $\log(t + 1)$.

5. **Breslow test (Breslow (NA)):**

Breslow et al. (1984) constructed a test for acceleration by additionally considering the rank or Nelson-Aalen estimator as time-dependent covariate in the Cox model:

6. **Piecewise exponential (lag) model (PWExp, PWExpLag):**

For the *piecewise exponential* models the baseline hazard is not unspecified but assumed to be piecewise constant.

Furthermore, the following regression models were considered.

7. **Additive hazard model (Aalen):**

The Aalen additive model assumes that $\lambda(t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$.

8. **Royston/Parmar spline model (Royston-Parmar PH/TD):**

Royston and Parmar (2002) proposed to model the logarithmic cumulative hazard function using restricted cubic splines for the cumulative baseline hazard

$$\log(\Lambda(t)) = s(\log(t)|\gamma, k) + \beta x.$$

If the treatment effect can not be assumed to be constant over time, the spline coefficient can be modelled to depend on treatment X .

9. **Accelerated failure time model (AFT):**

The AFT model assumes that $\log(T) = \beta x + \varepsilon$ where different distributions for ε are considered.

• **Other tests**

1. **Milestone (Mile NA):**

Comparison of the cumulative hazard rates at a fixed timepoint t_0 based on the Nelson-Aalen estimator.

2. **Linear and Quadratic combination (LLRNA, QLRNA):**

Logan et al. (2015) proposed to use a linear and quadratic combination of the Mile NA statistic at t_0 and the Landmark statistic starting at t_0 .

3. **K-sample omnibus non-proportional hazards (KONP):**

The KONP test uses a sample space partition as described by Gorfine et al. (2020).

4. **Checking PH approach (Check PH):**

The checking PH approach was proposed by Campbell and Dean (2014), where at first the PH assumption is assessed using Grambsch-Therneau (GT) at level α_{GT} and if GT is not significant Cox is used and, otherwise CoxTD.

5. **2-stage approach (Qiu-Sheng):**

Qiu and Sheng (2008) proposed a sequential two-stage approach: In the first stage, the overall treatment effect is tested at level α_1 using the logrank test. If the logrank test is significant, then the null hypothesis is rejected, otherwise a new logrank test is proposed to test if the hazards cross at the level α_2 .

6. **Minimum of logrank and CoxTD p-values (MinPv):**

Callegaro and Spiessens (2017) proposed an simple approach by defining the test statistic $\min(p_{G(0,0)}, p_{\text{CoxTD}})$.

7. **Joint test (joint Test):**

Royston and Parmar (2014) proposed a joint test as the sum of the Grambsch-Therneau test statistic and the Cox test statistic.

8. **Combined test (comb. Test):**

Later Royston and Parmar (2016) proposed to take the minimum of the p-value of the maximum RMST and the p-value from a Cox model.

9. **Cauchy changepoint test (CauchyCP):**

Zhang et al. (2021) proposed to perform single change-point Cox models at pre-specified change-points t_1^*, \dots, t_m^* and combine the p-values using the Cauchy combination method.

10. Net benefit:

Buyse (2010) extended the idea of the Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney test to survival data and estimates the net chance of longer survival called net benefit.

Some of these methods require that parameters for analysis are specified and to assess if those methods are sensitive with respect to parameter misspecification, the following choices have been implemented:

- **RMST:** The power of the test should be bigger the more information after the assumed delayed treatment effect is taken into consideration. As on the other hand the RMST is not estimable if the truncation time is bigger than the minimum of the last observed event times in both arms, the truncation time was chosen to be the minimum of the maximal follow-up time and the 90th percentile of the true distribution of the survival times in the control group.
- **Milestone analysis:** Milestone survival is often evaluated annually, and hence the 1-year or 2-year survival rates are chosen. If these exceeded the 90th percentile of the true distribution function of the survival times in the control group, the milestone survival was evaluated at this point.
- **Landmark analysis:** Landmark analysis considers only those individuals who have survived until a pre-specified landmark time and ignores the data before that time. Since the survival curves are identical until the change point t_1^* , the data before this time should not contribute to an estimated difference between treatments. Hence the following landmark times are considered:
 1. Too early: $0.9t_1^*$ in scenarios in which a delay exists and 0.1τ otherwise
 2. At change point t_1^* in scenarios in which a delay exists and 0.2τ otherwise
 3. Too late: $1.1t_1^*$ in scenarios in which a delay exists and 0.3τ otherwise
- **Generalized linear lag model:** To assess the robustness of the analysis against misspecification the following intervals $[t_1, t_2]$ are specified:

- If no delay exists, i.e. $t_2^* = 0$ then the intervals are chosen as

$$[0, 0.3\tau], [0, 0.2\tau], [0.1, 0.3\tau].$$

- If a delay exists, i.e. $t_2^* \neq 0$, but the effect is achieved instantly and does not increase linearly, i.e. $t_1^* = t_2^*$ then the intervals are chosen to be

$$[0.9t_2^*, 1.1t_2^*], [0.8t_2^*, 1.2t_2^*], [0.7t_2^*, 1.3t_2^*].$$

- If a delay exists, i.e. $t_2^* \neq 0$, and the effect increases linearly, i.e. $t_1^* \neq t_2^*$ then the following intervals are chosen:

1. Too big: Take the midpoint of the interval $\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2}$ and increase the width by 10%. This gives the interval $\left[\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2} \pm 1.1(t_2^* - t_1^*)\right]$.
2. Correct: The interval is taken to be the true interval $[t_1^*, t_2^*]$.
3. Too small: Take the midpoint of the interval $\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2}$ and decrease the width by 10%. This gives the interval $\left[\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2} \pm 0.9(t_2^* - t_1^*)\right]$.

Table 8: *Parameters for analysis in power scenarios*

Method	Also applicable to	Parameter
RMST	ABC	$\min(\tau - a, q_{C,0.9})$
Milestone	-	$\min(12, q_{C,0.9})$ and $\min(24, q_{C,0.9})$
Landmark	MWLR, Thres, PWExp, V0, ParGroup	PH scenarios: $0.1\tau, 0.2\tau, 0.3\tau$ NPH scenarios: $\begin{cases} 0.9 \cdot t_1^*, & \text{too early} \\ t_1^*, & \text{correct} \\ 1.1 \cdot t_1^*, & \text{too late} \end{cases}$
GenLin Model	PWExpLag, MERT, (m)Logit	PH scenarios: $[0, 0.3 \cdot \tau], [0, 0.2 \cdot \tau], [0.1 \cdot \tau, 0.3 \cdot \tau]$ Threshold lag scenarios: $[0.9 \cdot t_2^*, 1.1 \cdot t_2^*], [0.8 \cdot t_2^*, 1.2 \cdot t_2^*], [0.7 \cdot t_2^*, 1.3 \cdot t_2^*]$ Linear lag scenarios: $\begin{cases} \left[\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2} \pm 1.1 \cdot (t_2^* - t_1^*)\right], & \text{too big} \\ [t_1^*, t_2^*], & \text{correct} \\ \left[\frac{t_1^* + t_2^*}{2} \pm 0.9 \cdot (t_2^* - t_1^*)\right], & \text{too small} \end{cases}$

Here $q_{C,0.9}$ denotes the 90 % quantile of the distribution in the control arm.

Performance measure

The power was chosen as performance measure to evaluate the different methods. To control the Monte-Carlo standard error the number of simulated datasets n_{sim} was calculated as described by Morris et al. (2019).

The Monte-Carlo standard error is given by

$$\sqrt{\frac{\widehat{\text{Power}}(1 - \widehat{\text{Power}})}{n_{sim}}}.$$

and to keep it below 0.4% a total of $n_{sim} = 10000$ simulated datasets are needed.

3 Assessment of Type I error

In the following the ADEMP structure of the type I error assessment is described in detail.

Aim

To assess the type I error of the different methods in scenarios comparable to the scenarios considered in the power simulation.

Data-generating mechanism

The null scenarios, i.e. scenarios with equally distributed survival times in both arms, were chosen to be comparable to the power scenarios of the previous section. This reduces the parameters to

- The study duration $\tau = 6, 12, 24, 48, 60$
- Uniform accrual over the interval $[0, a]$, where $a = 0.2\tau, 0.4\tau$.
- Weibull distributed $\text{Wei}(\lambda_C, k_C)$ survival times with shape parameter $k_C = 0.5, 1, 2$ and scale parameter λ_C chosen in dependence on the median survival times of $\text{med}_C = 5, 15, 20$.

This results in total number of $5 \cdot 2 \cdot 3 \cdot 3 = 90$ scenarios. As type I error is (more or less) independent of the sample size n_{obs} was chosen to be the same as the sample size calculated for the full effect strategy of the maximal treatment effect $\theta = 0.5$.

Estimand and Methods

The same methods as for the power assessment were considered and as the choice of the parameters for analysis is somewhat arbitrary since there is no meaningful choice for null scenarios where survival times are equally distributed in both arms. However, as the choice of the parameters for analysis should not influence type I error they were set based on the choice of the parameters in the power scenario.

Table 9: *Parameters for analysis in power scenarios*

Method	Also applicable to	Parameter
RMST	ABC	$\min(\tau - a, q_{C,0.9})$
Milestone	-	$\min(12, q_{C,0.9})$ and $\min(24, q_{C,0.9})$
Landmark	MWLR, Thres, PW- Exp, V0, ParGroup	Mean over parameters from power scenarios
GenLin Model	PWExpLag, MERT, (m)Logit	Mean over parameters from power scenarios

Here $q_{C,0.9}$ denotes the 90 % quantile of the distribution in the control arm.

Performance measure

The type I error rate α was chosen as performance measure to evaluate the different methods and as for the power the number of simulated datasets was chosen to be $n_{sim} = 10000$.

The Monte-Carlo standard error is then given as

$$\sqrt{\frac{\hat{\alpha}(1 - \hat{\alpha})}{n_{sim}}} \approx 0.0022.$$

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